

Effect of magnetic activity on the detection of acoustic modes in solar-like stars

Savita Mathur^{1,2}, Rafael A. García³, Lisa Bugnet³, Ângela G. R. Santos⁴, Paul G. Beck^{1,2}, Netsha Santiago⁵

¹ Instituto de Astrofísica de Canarias (IAC), C/Va Lactea, s/n, E-38200 La Laguna, Tenerife, Spain

² Universidad de La Laguna (ULL), Departamento de Astrofísica, E-38206 La Laguna, Tenerife, Spain

³ AIM, CEA, CNRS, Université Paris-Saclay, Université Paris Diderot, Sorbonne Paris Cité, F-91191 Gif-sur-Yvette, France

⁴ Space Science Institute, 4750 Walnut street Suite 205, Boulder CO, 80301, USA

⁵ University of Puerto Rico, Puerto Rico

Abstract

During the first ten months of the *Kepler* mission, over 2000 stars were observed for one month in short cadence mode allowing us to look for stochastically excited acoustic modes. This led to the detection of solar-like oscillations in only about 520 stars. Chaplin *et al.* (2011a) explained the lack of detection in most of the other stars as a consequence of their high surface magnetic activity. However the sample of stars studied was polluted with many classical pulsators and red giants. Here, we re-visit the study on a cleaner sample of stars where we have removed stars with newly detected oscillations using the latest DR25 from *Kepler* along with the classical pulsators and red giants that were polluting the sample. For the remaining main-sequence solar-like stars, we measured the rotation and magnetic activity proxy based on photometric data (called S_{ph}). While close to half of this sample has an S_{ph} value larger than the one of the Sun, we find that a large fraction of stars without oscillations detected have a low magnetic activity level, which was unexpected. We also investigate on the origin of these missing detections using new spectroscopic observations of those stars (in particular in terms of metallicity and chromospheric activity). An upper limit of S_{ph} is also inferred as a limit above which no pulsations were detected. Understanding the non-detection of solar-like oscillations is key to predict the yield of solar-like pulsating stars for missions such as TESS and PLATO where the detection of solar-like oscillations will allow us to better characterize the stars, in particular the ones hosting planets.

1 Introduction

Asteroseismology has proved to be a very powerful tool to determine stellar parameters such as mass, radius, and age (e.g. Pinsonneault *et al.*, 2014; Serenelli *et al.*, 2017). Having detection of acoustic modes is thus an important asset for not only characterizing stars, but also to characterize exoplanets (e.g. Howell *et al.*, 2012; Huber *et al.*, 2013; Silva Aguirre *et al.*, 2015; Van Eylen *et al.*, 2018), binary-star systems (Beck *et al.*, 2014) or for galactic-archeology studies (Martig *et al.*, 2015; Anders *et al.*, 2017). This synergy between asteroseismology and other fields has been developed in the last few years in particular, thanks to the high-quality photometric data collected by the *Kepler* (Borucki *et al.*, 2010) and CoRoT (Convection, Rotation, and Transits Baglin *et al.*, 2006) missions.

Out of ~ 2500 solar-like stars observed in short cadence for 1 month during the *Kepler* survey phase: we detected oscillations in only 518 stars (Chaplin *et al.*, 2011b), representing only 20% of the sample. Chaplin *et al.* (2011a) measured the level of magnetic activity based on the standard deviation of the lightcurve and found that the level of magnetic activity of the non-detection stars is higher than for the stars with detections of p modes. Indeed, we know that magnetic activity suppresses the amplitude of the modes for the Sun as it has been shown thanks to the long dataset obtained to perform helioseismology (e.g. Salabert *et al.*, 2009). This similar phenomenon was observed in another solar-like stars, HD49933, targeted by the CoRoT mission, allowing us to discover an ongoing magnetic cycle in an F-type star using seismology

(García *et al.*, 2010). More recently, many groups have been looking at the changes in the frequencies and amplitudes of the modes of the solar-like stars observed by *Kepler* and this has now been detected in around a hundred stars (Salabert *et al.*, 2016b; Kiefer *et al.*, 2017; Santos *et al.*, 2018)

In this work, we re-do the analysis done by Chaplin *et al.* (2011a) but for a cleaner sample of stars that is not polluted by other stars and using the final lightcurves lasting for up to four years. We also look at other stellar parameters to understand the different reasons for the hampered acoustic modes. The full detailed analysis will be presented in Mathur *et al.* (in prep.).

2 Building the sample of stars

We started with the full sample of 2500 stars that were observed for 1 month in short-cadence during the survey phase of the *Kepler* mission. We used the DR25 processed long-cadence lightcurves to which we applied the corrections following García *et al.* (2011). This allowed us to have four-year long lightcurves in most stars. We also filled regular gaps smaller than 20 days using the inpainting technique (García *et al.*, 2014b; Pires *et al.*, 2015). We finally applied three different high-pass triangular filters of 20, 55, and 80 days. The visual check of the lightcurves and power spectra showed that the sample contained red giants misclassified in the *Kepler* Input Catalog (Brown *et al.*, 2011), which were re-classified based on seismic diagnostics by Mathur *et al.* (2016), classical pulsators, polluted stars by close binaries or by instrumental

Figure 1: HR diagram of the 1486 stars observed in SC during the survey phase without solar-like oscillations detections (black) and the 518 stars with solar-like oscillations detections in Chaplin *et al.* (2011a). The stellar parameters are from Mathur *et al.* (2017).

problems.

We also analyzed the short-cadence lightcurves of these stars with the asteroseismic pipeline, A2Z (Mathur *et al.*, 2010) and the FliPer metric (Bugnet *et al.*, 2018), to look for additional detections of solar-like oscillations. Indeed, the detections of Chaplin *et al.* (2011a) were based on lightcurves processed in the early dates of the mission. With the DR25, we detected solar-like oscillation in almost 100 additional stars. This yields a clean sample of around 1,500 stars that are supposed to be main-sequence solar-like stars but for which no acoustic modes have been detected. This sample is represented in Figure 1.

3 Methodology: rotation periods and magnetic activity

3.1 Surface Rotation

The variability seen in the photometric lightcurves can have several origins: oscillations, convection, rotation, and photon noise. In the past, many works have been led to measure surface rotation in the *Kepler* lightcurves (e.g. McQuillan *et al.*, 2014; García *et al.*, 2014a), including solar analogs (Salabert *et al.*, 2016a). Indeed, we can measure the surface rotation through the passage spots on the visible disk. Different methods can be used to measure the period of that modulation: compute the classical periodogram, do a time-frequency analysis, or compute the autocorrelation function (ACF). Our method (García *et al.*, 2014a; Ceillier *et al.*, 2016, 2017) combines the time-frequency analysis based on wavelets (Torrence & Compo, 1998; Mathur *et al.*, 2010) and the autocorrelation function. When both methods agree with the three different filters, the results is picked as reliable. It was shown by (Aigrain *et al.*, 2015), based on simulations and hare-and-hounds, that this method provides the best results in terms of reliability and completeness.

Figure 2: Distribution of the rotation period, P_{rot} . The different panels correspond to different groups of stars as described in the text: red for hot stars, blue for cool stars, and green for subgiants. The black dashed line is the histogram for the full sample of stars where rotation period was measured.

3.2 Magnetic Activity

Given that the measurement of the rotation period is based on the active regions/spots present at the surface of the stars, we can measure the level of activity of the stars from the standard deviation of the lightcurves. Knowing the rotation period, we have defined the metric S_{ph} (Mathur *et al.*, 2014a,b) as the measure of the level of magnetic activity. It is measured by computing the standard deviation of subsamples of length 5 times the rotation period, which ensures that we are not measuring any other kind of variability. It was also shown that this metric is a good representation of the magnetic activity of the stars by comparing the S_{ph} with other classical proxies of magnetic activity for the Sun (Salabert *et al.*, 2017). Indeed, they found more than 80% of correlation between the S_{ph} and the other proxies of magnetic activity.

4 Results

With our pipeline, we have detected reliable rotation periods for ~ 800 stars on the main sequence. The distribution of the rotation period and S_{ph} of these stars is shown in Figures 2 and 3 where we divided the stars into three groups as in (García *et al.*, 2014a): cool stars with T_{eff} below 5500K, hot stars with T_{eff} larger than 5500K and the subgiants with $\log g < 3.6$ dex. We notice that the hot stars rotate generally faster while the subgiants rotate slightly slower.

We also have a subsample of 600 stars that we need to check visually as all the methods do not agree. However, among the reliable stars, we obtain that 49.5% of them are above the maximum level of the Sun. For that subsample, the high level of magnetic activity explains the non-detection of the modes. For the remaining stars, we need to investigate other reasons for the non-detection. Here is a list of possible paths to look at:

- Inclination angle can lead to smaller S_{ph} , thus S_{ph} is a lower limit;
- Presence of companion (tidal interaction) can also lead

Figure 3: Distribution of the magnetic activity index, S_{ph} . The different panels correspond to different groups of stars as described in the text: red for hot stars, blue for cool stars, and green for subgiants. The black dashed line is the histogram for the full sample of stars where rotation period, and thus S_{ph} was measured.

to suppressed modes as observed by Gaulme *et al.* (2014) for red giants in eclipsing binaries. Beck *et al.* (2018) connected the non-presence of oscillation modes to short circularization time scales. Some binary systems have also been discovered in solar analogs (Beck *et al.*, 2017);

- Result from the automatic analysis with the A2Z pipeline of the short cadence data to look for acoustic modes might still miss some detection for the low signal-to-noise ratio stars
- Metallicity could also have an impact on the amplitude of the modes as shown by Samadi *et al.* (2010). Indeed, a higher metallicity will change the opacity and the excitation of the modes. For all the stars, we have metallicity from the DR14 of APOGEE (Apache POint Galactic Evolution Experiment Majewski *et al.*, 2017; Abolfathi *et al.*, 2018). We find that the mean $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ of these stars is -0.16 dex. This is not what we expected and more investigation has to be done.

For that sample of non-oscillating stars, we started spectroscopic follow up with the HERMES spectrograph on the 1.2m Mercator telescope at La Palma (Raskin, 2011; Raskin *et al.*, 2011) to measure metallicity and derive the Mount-Wilson S -index from the Ca H&K lines as proxy for the magnetic activity (see Beck *et al.*, 2016, for more details). We already obtained 14 nights between 2015 and 2017. Preliminary results for a few stars show that in general they are indeed very active though a few stars with low activity are also present in the sample. More observations were also done in summer 2018 and will be analyzed soon.

5 Conclusions

We have seen that almost half of the sample for which we have obtained reliable rotation periods and that do not have detections of oscillations is more active than the Sun. We are

still investigating the reasons for not detecting the acoustic modes (close-by companion, low-signal-to-noise ratio of the modes, metallicity) or underestimating the magnetic activity levels of the stars due to the inclination angle. The full analysis of this sample will be presented in Mathur *et al.* (in prep.). Understanding the non detection of the modes is crucial for missions such as TESS (Ricker *et al.*, 2015) and PLATO (Rauer *et al.*, 2014) as they rely on detecting oscillations to better characterize the exoplanet found around the star.

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